

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH "DEMOKRITOS"

European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

65th ESReDA Seminar

*From risk imagination to safety intervention -
Managing risks with knowledge*

November 14–15, 2024

NCSR Demokritos, Athens, Greece

With the kind support of:

European Safety and Reliability Association and

Keynote Lecture 2

Technical Language Processing – unlocking information in safety data

Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz CEng, FTSE

In the safety domain we look back to inform the way forward. Our approach to identifying and prioritising risks, the controls we select, and the measures we use to assess the effectiveness of these controls is informed by what has happened in the past. In practice this has meant more reliance on the memories of our people and their life experiences than on the data captured in activity, event and investigation databases, spreadsheets, and reports.

This historical data, particularly unstructured text descriptions, is rich in information but is difficult to find, search, extract and transform into useful information efficiently. To complicate matters further, event type and cause identification, labelling and classification is done by one human and seldom reviewed or checked by others. As a result, the meaning of labels is often ambiguous, and this leads to differences in interpretation when data is read by other than the original author. When dealing with data exchange, laborious manual alignment is often required. Terms such as failure mode, failure mechanism, root cause, failure cause, are often used and interpreted differently within and across organisations. And when looking for specific concepts, the analyst needs to know all plausible spellings and conceptual alternatives used to describe the concept. For example, when looking for lubrication-problems the search may need at least the following keywords ‘oil’, ‘lube’, ‘filter’, ‘hydraulic’, ‘sample’, ‘oil hose’, ‘oily’, ‘grease’, and ‘degrease’ as well as various misspellings.

There is limited quality control on classification tasks. For example, should ‘the pipe ruptured’ be put in the class ‘exploded’, ‘deformed’ or ‘cracked’ if these are the only options in your corporate failure mechanism list? Many classification codes (e.g. “near-miss”, “corrosion”, “likelihood-low”) are subsequently used for all sorts of downstream analysis and reporting so being consistent in how they are used is important. Estimates for failure rates are often based on simplified counts of events rather than on actual time between events and whether the event is a failure or suspension. The count-based approach can lead to mean time to failure estimates of half their actual value resulting in over maintenance [1].

We do not have to accept this situation any longer due to developments in Technical Language Processing (TLP) enabled by text-based AI [2]. Industrial organisations (and regulators) can now data mine information from their own internal historical records. We can extract information from unstructured texts such as maintenance work orders, incident reports and root cause analyses. TLP developments will unlock a treasure trove of historical data for safety professionals to examine. However, this will not happen quickly if every organisation approaches this on their own and in their own way. There is a need for an open approach so that TLP artefacts can be examined, shared, and reused.

To do this Standards and Industrial bodies need to take the lead in providing Linked Data platforms for shared vocabularies and ontologies, academics who publish papers on ontologies must provide GitHub access to the annotated ontology artefacts (and reviewers should demand this), and we should encourage and support the publication of annotated training data for transformer and Gen AI model fine-tuning [3].

This talk provides an overview view of text-based AI grouping applications by a) Narrow AI, b) Generative AI (GenAI) and c) Logic-based AI. Narrow AI describes AI tools used to perform specific language tasks with high proficiency. It is good for repetitive processes and patterns, for problems with a narrow scope, and for which training data is available. Examples include classification, translation, digital assistance, and email filtering. GenAI uses large language models (LLM) to perform a wide range of tasks. GenAI generates responses to given prompts by continuously predicting the most likely word given the previous word(s), and exhibits strong performance due to training on billions of examples. Logic-based AI is used for reasoning tasks and is appropriate when rigor is needed to draw conclusions from facts and rules, apply logical inference, and for semantic interoperability.

We draw on lessons the UWA NLP-TLP group has learned from working with industry, government, and standards body partners to developing open software tools, data sets, fine-tuned models, and ontologies for maintenance and reliability applications over the last 8 years. Examples of solutions to extracting knowledge from technical texts [3, 4], classification of failure modes [5], data quality [6], causal analysis [7] and semantic interoperability [8] are provided.

One of the key lessons we share is that many real industrial problems need to use a combination of narrow AI, Gen AI, and logic-based AI in their end-to-end pipelines. Another is that to ensure uptake by industry we have made our schemas, the data developed from annotation and used in constructing knowledge graphs, and the ontological concepts developed, available in open-source repositories and, where appropriate, using Linked Data. This has enabled our artefacts to be adopted and extended both within our group, by industry and by other research groups. This is an approach we encourage others to follow.

We believe the foundations of AI for enterprise safety applications depend on 1) industry having access to Linked Data concepts that are shared and accessible by humans, enterprise systems and AI applications, 2) being able to ground LLMs models to minimise hallucinations and tailor them to the context of the enterprise (using a technique called RAG), and 3) improving data quality as AI models are only as good as the data they are built on.

References

- [1] Bikaun, T. and Hodkiewicz, M., 2021, June. Semi-automated estimation of reliability measures from maintenance work order records. In PHM Society European Conference (Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 9-9).
- [2] Brundage, M.P., Sexton, T., Hodkiewicz, M., Dima, A. and Lukens, S., 2021. Technical language processing: Unlocking maintenance knowledge. *Manufacturing Letters*, 27, pp.42-46.
- [3] Bikaun, T.K., French, T., Stewart, M., Liu, W. and Hodkiewicz, M., 2024, May. MaintIE: A Fine-Grained Annotation Schema and Benchmark for Information Extraction from Maintenance Short Texts. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024)* (pp. 10939-10951).

- [4] Stewart, M., Hodkiewicz, M., Liu, W. and French, T., 2022. MWO2KG and Echidna: Constructing and exploring knowledge graphs from maintenance data. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part O: Journal of Risk and Reliability, p.1748006X221131128.
- [5] Stewart, M., Hodkiewicz, M. and Li, S., 2023. Large language models for failure mode classification: an investigation. arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.08181.
- [6] Woods, C., Selway, M., Bikaun, T., Stumptner, M. and Hodkiewicz, M., 2024. An ontology for maintenance activities and its application to data quality. Semantic Web, 15(2), pp.319-352.
- [7] Hershowitz, B., Hodkiewicz, M., Bikaun, T., Stewart, M. and Liu, W., 2024. Causal knowledge extraction from long text maintenance documents. Computers in Industry, 161, p.104110.
- [8] Woods, C., Hodkiewicz, M. and French, T., 2024. Semantic Quality Assurance of Industrial Maintenance Procedures. IEEE Access (early access).